

Variation in stoichiometry and mechanism of some redox systems[†]

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Keywords : Reaction mechanism, redox system, stoichiometry.

Introduction

The determination of stoichiometry and identification and quantitative estimation of the end product, is the first thing that one does in a kinetic and mechanistic study. Although this may just give information about the extent of reaction and hardly anything about the mechanism, the difficulties and complications in its determination help one to substantiate the mechanism obtained by employing other tools, and in some cases stoichiometry itself may

lead one to a possible mechanism. Role of stoichiometry is further highlighted if one can identify the intermediate products, if any. Very often one would find that the stoichiometry varies with the change in the acidity (pH), temperature, ratio of the reactant concentrations, and in the presence of a catalyst or some other foreign constituent which influences the rate of reaction. This situation too is quite helpful in knowing the mechanism of a reaction. Can we now say whether there is any worthwhile

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#This is not a general or comprehensive article. Some specific systems only, presenting special features have been described.

relationship between stoichiometry and mechanism just as we have for the 'hydrogen-ion dependence of rate and mechanism¹', 'catalysis in inorganic reactions and mechanism²', 'concentration dependence of reaction rates and mechanism³', and 'ionic strength of the medium and mechanism⁴'? Such a systematised knowledge cannot be given in case of stoichiometry since the latter does not depend on the rate of reaction. One has to appreciate the fact that the variation in the stoichiometry under different conditions is helpful to indicate the probable path of reaction and that should be enough in a mechanistic study. The point to be stressed is that wherever stoichiometry in a reaction is variable, the fact should be exploited i.e. it should be thoroughly investigated to know its contribution to the mechanism. The purpose of this article is to describe some of such situations where a determination of stoichiometry and its variation, and the identification of the products, have been useful in obtaining an outline for the mechanism of the reaction.

Reduction of peroxodisulphate

The thermal decomposition⁵ of peroxodisulphate is a very slow process according to the following eq. (1),

Several organic substances such as oxalate⁶, thiosulphate⁷, formate⁸ etc. are known to be oxidised slowly by different chain mechanisms involving SO_4^- radical. Metal ions like Mn^{II} , Ce^{III} , Cr^{III} , V^{III} etc. are very slow to react with peroxodisulphate and no kinetic study seems to have been made. Fe^{II} ,^{9,10} alone is known to react with $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ according to the following stoichiometric eq. (3),

and mechanism (4) and (5) in low acid ($<0.01 \text{ M}$) solutions.

Kolthoff and coworkers⁹ found the stoichiometry to change upon slow addition of Fe^{II} to peroxodisulphate and a systematic study¹⁰ at different $[\text{H}^+]$, yields following stoichiometry (6) and mechanism (7), (8) and (9).

Thus the change in the stoichiometry ($\Delta[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]/\Delta[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]$) from 1 : 2 in low acid medium to 1 : 1 in high acid medium indicates a change in the mechanism. This leads to the conclusion that SO_4^- reacts preferably with H_2O than with Fe^{II} depending on the hydrogen ion concentration, or protonated SO_4^- reacts with H_2O to give oxygen rather than with Fe^{II} .

This competence of SO_4^- to react with H_2O (with oxygen as the product) leading to a variation in the stoichiometry and mechanism, is exhibited in some of Ag^{I} catalysed oxidations of peroxodisulphate too. Several metallic ion substrates such as Mn^{II} ,¹¹, Ce^{III} ,¹², Cr^{III} ,¹³, VO^{2+} ,¹⁴, Tl^{I} ,¹⁵ etc. are oxidised by this system and all of them have expected stoichiometry and give similar rate laws and similar rate constants conforming to a common rate determining step (10) as follows.

Direct reaction¹⁶ between peroxodisulphate and Ag^{I} has also been studied and in all cases the second order rate constant has a value of $(1.0 \text{ to } 1.4) \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 35° . A reinvestigation¹⁷ of the oxidation of Ce^{III} by the same system of $(\text{SO}_8^{2-} + \text{Ag}^+)$, yielded an unexpected and different stoichiometry of 1 : 1 instead of 1 : 2, though giving the same rate constant found earlier¹². The stoichiometry was as in eq. (11), and once again it indicates that the reaction of SO_4^- with H_2O is preferred as compared with Ce^{III} .

This is in contrast with the reaction of SO_4^- with Mn^{II} , Cr^{III} , VO^{2+} and Tl^{I} which is faster than that of SO_4^- with H_2O .

The oxidation of hyponitrous acid¹⁸ with $(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-} + \text{Ag}^+)$ system is a reaction which has provided maximum information about the reduction of peroxodisulphate and the role of SO_4^- in its preferential reaction with water. This was possible once again with an unexpected complicated stoichiometry of the reaction as given in eq. (12).

If it were a reaction on the same lines as mentioned for various metal ions, following stoichiometry (13) would have resulted.

But this was not to be because there are two independent paths. One of them is (14),

The other path is (15a) and (15b) followed by fast steps involving two more moles of peroxodisulphate.

The stoichiometric equations for the two paths are (16) and (17).

Incidentally the products in the two paths are the same. There was an additional information that $k_0 = 2k_1$ for a number of sets of concentrations and as seen from Fig. 1 for one set. Since (14) and (15) (a and b) occur simultaneously, eq. (16) has to be multiplied by 2 and then the two eqs. (16) and (17) can be added to calculate

Fig. 1. Oxidation of H₂N₂O₂ with (S₂O₈²⁻ + Ag^I) system.

the overall stoichiometry which turns out to be (12). Incidentally this is first system of (S₂O₈²⁻ + Ag⁺) where there is kinetic evidence for complex formation between S₂O₈²⁻ and Ag⁺ though it has been guessed in a number of reactions in view of its complex formation with Cu²⁺,¹⁹ Fe³⁺,²⁰ and Co³⁺.²¹ Yet another fact that the stoichiometry of this reaction changes to (12a) in the presence of acrylamide and no oxygen is evolved, supports the mechanism given above (i.e. eqs. (14) × 2 + (15a) and (15b)) without involving two more moles of peroxodisulphate in the latter path.

Acrylamide consumes HN₂O₂ and SO₄⁻ and there is no further reaction with peroxodisulphate. The oxidation of H₂N₂O₂ by (S₂O₈²⁻ + Ag⁺) system shows that SO₄⁻ reacts with water and not with H₂N₂O₂ or Ag^I. Incidentally all oxidations with this system show that Ag²⁺ reacts faster with the substrate, and water is not oxidised. The reaction of Ag^{II} with water is known to be slow²².

Yet another reaction which shows the role of SO₄⁻, is the Cu^{II} catalysed oxidation of hydrazine^{19b} with peroxodisulphate with the following stoichiometry (18).

Since nitrogen and ammonia were obtained, it seemed to undergo one electron change according to the stoichiometry²³ ($\Delta[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]/\Delta[\text{N}_2\text{H}_4]$ of 1 : 2 but the actual stoichiometry was found to be 1 : 1 which made one look for another electron change of S₂O₈²⁻ and the product of oxygen. Oxygen did exist there showing that SO₄⁻ reacts with H₂O and not with N₂H₄ or its oxidation product.

Oxidation of hydrazine

Oxidation of hydrazine²⁴ with different oxidants in one electron change with nitrogen and ammonia as products, and in four electron change with nitrogen only as a product, depends on the relative concentrations of the reactants, acidity, temperature and the type of the oxidant, and consequently the stoichiometry ($\Delta[\text{oxidant}]/\Delta[\text{N}_2\text{H}_4]$) of the reaction will change according to the conditions. It has been reported^{23,24} that if hydrazine undergoes one electron change as shown in (19), hydrazyl radical is formed which dimerises and subsequently decomposes to yield N₂ and NH₃.

Table 1. Extents of the one- and four-electron changes in $Ce^{IV}-N_2H_4$ reaction and observed stoichiometry in 2 M $HClO_4$

$10^2[Ce^{IV}]/M$	$10^2[N_2H_5^+]/M$	$\frac{[Ce^{IV}] \text{ used}}{[N_2H_5^+] \text{ used}}$	$10^3[NH_3]/M$	% of one-electron change		Calcd. stoichiometry
				calculated from the amount of ammonia (A)	% of four-electron change (100 - A) (B)	
5.00	1.60	2.95	6.00	37.5	62.5	2.88
5.83	1.33	3.18	3.66	27.5	72.5	3.175
5.00	1.60	3.09	4.80	30.0	70.0	3.10

In the four electron change, the oxidation occurs as shown in (20) yielding nitrogen.

The fate of hydrazyl radical is thus decided in two ways depending on the conditions.

In the oxidation with $Ce^{IV,25}$ in H_2SO_4 solutions, the expected stoichiometry ($\Delta[Ce^{IV}]/\Delta[N_2H_4]$) is 1 : 1 or 4 : 1, but it varies between 1 : 1 and 4 : 1 and that limiting stoichiometry (1 : 1) is obtained when $[H_2SO_4]$ is 10 molar or above. Hence after the rate controlling reactions ($Ce(SO_4)_2 + N_2H_5^+$) and ($Ce(SO_4)_2 + N_2H_4$), one or both of the fast reactions (19) and (20) occur yielding the products. In $HClO_4$ solutions both the fast reactions occur as per stoichiometries of 1 : 1 and 4 : 1 and the two can be separately calculated as shown in Table 1. There is more than satisfactory agreement between the calculated and experimental values for the overall stoichiometry. However, the two reactions (19) and (20) being fast, their exact nature is not known. Another fact to be noted in the reaction is that the reaction becomes very slow requiring 45 to 50 days for the determination of stoichiometry in high $[H_2SO_4]$ solutions, probably because of the decrease in the rate with the increase of H^+ and HSO_4^- .

Iron(III) catalysed oxidation²⁰ of hydrazine with peroxodisulphate shows the same behaviour as found in the Cu^{II} catalysed^{19b} oxidation as in (21),

but in addition a variation in stoichiometry ($\Delta[S_2O_8^{2-}]/\Delta[N_2H_5^+]$) from 1 : 1 to 1 : 2 was also found, and the content of oxygen decreased and that of nitrogen increased. This clearly shows that SO_4^- radical reacts with N_2H_3 radical rather than with H_2O . Incidentally this also shows

that the reactions ($SO_4^- + H_2O$) and ($SO_4^- + N_2H_3$) are competitive. In any case there is change in the mechanism with the variation in the stoichiometry.

Oxidation of hydrazine with $Fe^{III,26}$ in $HClO_4$ solutions is a slow process which occurs with the following stoichiometry (22) and mechanism (23a) and (23b)

and it has the following rate law (24),

$$-d[Fe^{III}]/dt = K_H k_1 k_3 [Fe^{III}] [N_2H_5^+]^2 / [H^+] (k_2 [Fe^{II}] + k_3 [N_2H_5^+]) \quad (24)$$

where $K_H (= 4.84 \times 10^{-3}$ at 55°) is the hydrolytic constant of Fe^{3+} . The stoichiometry ($\Delta[Fe^{III}]/\Delta[N_2H_5^+]$) was 1 : 1 when the ratio of the initial concentrations of Fe^{III} and hydrazine was less than 10. On increasing the ratio, the stoichiometry tends to change to 4 : 1 and the mechanism also changes since the first order plot in Fe^{III} deviated from the straight line. The reaction becomes very slow on account of Fe^{II} being in the denominator of the rate law (24). The change in the mechanism involves a dimer formation of Fe^{3+} but the details are not given.

There is one regularity in the oxidations of hydrazine with respect to the oxidants. With one electron oxidants like $Ce^{IV,25}$, $Fe^{III,26}$, $Mn^{III,27}$ and $Cr^{III,28}$ the stoichiometry is 1 : 1 with nitrogen and ammonia as the products. With two or more electron change oxidants like $Tl^{III,29}$, $Cr^{VI,30}$, $H_2O_2^{31}$, $Pt^{IV,32}$, CAT^{33} , peroxodiphosphate³⁴, peroxomonophosphate³⁵ etc., the stoichiometry is 2 : 1 since the oxidants undergo four electron change for hydrazine. Hence the first step for the oxidation of hydrazine in one electron change involves the formation of hydrazyl radical which can react with the reactive intermediate of the oxidant, if available, and form N_2H_2

and finally nitrogen. If such a situation does not exist, hydrazyl radical undergoes internal disproportionation i.e. one nitrogen gets oxidised to nitrogen at the expense of another nitrogen which forms ammonia.

Oxidation of hydroxylamine

Several workers³⁶ have reported that the oxidation of hydroxylamine with different oxidants occurs with a variable stoichiometry, depending on the ratio of initial concentrations of the reactants, pH³⁷, temperature³⁸ and light conditions³⁹. The products are nitrogen, hyponitrous acid (H₂N₂O₂) or nitrous oxide gas, nitrite and nitrate. The major factor controlling the stoichiometry ($\Delta[\text{oxidant}]/\Delta[\text{hydroxylamine}]$) which on becoming large, increases the number of moles of oxidant reacting with one mole of hydroxylamine, with a change in the products in the sequence given above. Since in most cases the subsequent reactions are fast or much faster than the rate determining step producing H₂N₂O₂, the mechanism essentially does not change, but it does change or becomes complicated when the subsequent steps are competitive. In general if hydroxylamine is in excess, there is two electron change from N (-1) to N (+1) and H₂N₂O₂ is the product. The latter is obtained via intermediate formation of HNO which dimerizes yielding hyponitrous acid. The latter exists in *cis*- or *trans*-forms⁴⁰. The *trans*-form is stable⁴¹ but *cis*-form decomposes to N₂O. Such oxidants are H₂O₂⁴², HNO₂^{40,43}, Fe^{III},³⁸ Ce^{IV},^{36c}, Mn^{III},^{36e}, peroxonitrite^{36f} and iodate and periodate⁴⁴. One electron change from N (-1) to N (0) with nitrogen as the product occurs in oxidations by Fe^{III},⁴⁵ iodine⁴⁶, hexacyanoferrate^{III},⁴⁷ and vanadium(V)⁴⁸ when excess hydroxylamine is employed. In slow oxidations with peroxodisulphate and peroxodiphosphate and excess hydroxylamine, N₂O is the product, and so also in the Ag^I catalysed reactions (peroxodiphosphate⁴⁹ and peroxodisulphate⁵⁰). In all these oxidations of hydroxylamine whether N₂ or N₂O is the product, simple bimolecular mechanism is said to operate and any complication arises on account of other factors like complex formation, protonation etc. and not the change of stoichiometry.

With excess hydroxylamine, the oxidation by peroxomonophosphoric acid (H₃PO₅)⁵¹ is slow and occurs by a simple bimolecular mechanism with a stoichiometry (25) given below.

and a rate law (26) given below,

$$-d[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_5]/dt = k_1[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_5][\text{NH}_3\text{OH}^+] \\ (k_1 = 1.15 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ at } 45^\circ) \quad (27)$$

The stoichiometry was determined in the presence of small concentrations of iodide ($1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$) which greatly catalyse the reaction. The mechanism and the rate law in the presence of iodide change and the rate law becomes (27) but the stoichiometry does not change.

$$-d[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_5]/dt = [\text{H}_3\text{PO}_5](k_1[\text{NH}_3\text{OH}^+] + \\ k_3[\text{I}^-] + k_4[\text{NH}_3\text{OH}^+][\text{I}^-]) \quad (27) \\ (k_3 = 1.45 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ and } k_4 = 1.64 \times 10^4 \\ \text{M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ at } 45^\circ)$$

However, the stoichiometry is greatly susceptible to the initial ratio of [H₃PO₅] to [NH₃OH⁺]. If [H₃PO₅] > 5[NH₃OH⁺], nitrate is the product and the stoichiometry is about 3 : 1 corresponding to six electron change. In the presence of sulphamic acid, four electron change occurs with the stoichiometry of 2 : 1 and HNO₂ as the product. If [NH₃OH⁺] > 10[H₃PO₅], H₂N₂O₂ is the product as shown in (25) which was identified and estimated spectrophotometrically (peak at 207 nm with ϵ value⁵² of $4.61 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$; in 0.02 M NaOH peak at 232 nm corresponding to HN₂O₂⁻; in 1.0 M NaOH peak⁵³ at 248 nm). If H₂N₂O₂ is allowed to decompose in appropriate solution (pH = 9), N₂O is obtained which could be estimated volumetrically. This accounts for 95% N₂O. Fe^{III} is also a catalyst with the same stoichiometry (25) but with a different mechanism and rate law (28).

$$-d[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_5]/dt = [\text{H}_3\text{PO}_5][\text{NH}_3\text{OH}^+](k_1 + k_2[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]) \\ (k_2 = 1.5 \times 10^2 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ at } 45^\circ) \quad (28)$$

More information is obtained about stoichiometry and mechanism of the oxidation of hydroxylamine with Tl^{III},⁵⁴ in HClO₄ solutions (~0.5 M). The reaction occurs with the following stoichiometry (29),

and the rate law is (30) with a simple bimolecular mechanism involving TlOH²⁺ and NH₃OH⁺,

$$-d[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]/dt = kK_{\text{H}}[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}][\text{NH}_3\text{OH}^+]/([\text{H}^+] + K_{\text{H}}) \quad (30) \\ (k = 65.4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ at } 25^\circ)$$

where K_{H} is the hydrolytic constant of Tl³⁺ = 0.078 at 25° and [NH₃OH⁺] is in excess. If [Tl^{III}] > 3[NH₃OH⁺], stoichiometry ($\Delta[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]/\Delta[\text{NH}_3\text{OH}^+]$) was found to be 2.9 (~3.0), after keeping the reaction mixture for a long time (~a week) or by heating at 70–80° for 20 min

leading to reaction (31).

When the mixture is kept for 1 or 2 h, nitrite is the product according to the stoichiometry of 2 : 1. Reaction when carried out in the presence of sulphamic acid, also corresponds to the stoichiometry of 2 : 1 as per following reaction (32).

Complication can arise in this reaction⁵⁴ and in the previous reaction⁵¹, and perhaps other reactions too by employing $[\text{oxidant}] > [\text{NH}_3\text{OH}^+]$, on account of reaction of the products with the oxidant or hydroxylamine and also by the reaction between the products themselves as shown below for the present reaction.

k for (33) was obtained by mixing equivalent amounts of Tl^{III} and hydroxylamine which would give $\text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ and then further amounts of Tl^{III} were added to follow the kinetics. Reaction (34) is likely to be slower than other reactions. It appears that the only competitive reaction is (33) since the k value for (30) is $65.4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. In fact reaction (33) is more complicated than as shown. A separate study⁵⁷ of this reaction in the presence of 0.015 M EDTA and $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ NO_2^- to eliminate the induction period and obtain reproducibility, yielded a rate constant of $0.56 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 35° and 1.7 M H^+ .

In boiling acidic solutions of hydroxylamine and Fe^{III} , the reaction occurs as in (38)

but later the reaction was reported³⁹ to be complex from

the viewpoint of stoichiometry. Both N_2 and N_2O were found to be the products in a dark reaction³⁸, nitrogen according to the stoichiometry ($\Delta[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]/\Delta[\text{NH}_3\text{OH}^+]$) of 1 : 1 and nitrous oxide according to the stoichiometry of 2 : 1. Recent study⁴⁵ carried out in diffuse sunlight gave nitrogen according to 1 : 1 stoichiometry, but in partially dark reaction both N_2 and N_2O were obtained as per stoichiometries of both the reactions. Incidentally this was the first oxidation of hydroxylamine where the stoichiometry does not depend on the ratio of the concentrations of the reactants. N_2 and N_2O were estimated volumetrically, N_2O being collected over water saturated with N_2O obtained⁴⁰ from the reaction of concentrated solutions of nitrite and hydroxylamine hydrochloride. In diffuse sunlight, the reaction occurs according to the stoichiometry of 1 : 1 (38a)

with the mechanism as in (39) and (40), and the rate law (41).

Fig. 2. UV spectrum of reaction mixtures 2.5 min after mixing at pH 4.05, $[\text{NH}_3\text{OH}^+] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3}$ and $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. (a) In the dark, $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}] = 4.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (b) in the light, $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}] = 4.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Apparently the reaction in the light and dark seems to follow the same mechanism and the rate law, with the only difference that in the dark reaction the order in Fe^{III} decreased from one to zero in the presence of Fe^{II} . One could know the difference in the mechanism of the two reactions by carrying out spectrophotometric analysis of the reacting solutions of light and dark reactions after chosen intervals of time. Fig. 2 gives such results in which curve (b) for absorption for light reaction is for ten times the concentration of Fe^{III} than that for curve (a) for dark reaction. From the spectrophotometric results, it is obvious that the forward reaction (39) of the mechanism involves three steps, (1) rapid formation of the first precursor complex, (2) rapid formation of second precursor complex, and then (3) slow redox reaction yielding Fe^{II} and still another short lived complex species of Fe^{III} and oxidised moiety of NH_3OH^+ . The complete mechanism

is shown below.

Fig. 2 refers to the complexes 3 and 4 or perhaps 4 and 6 of the mechanism. The absorption of the complex of the dark reaction (a) has a far larger molar extinction coefficient (peak at 290 nm) than that of light sensitive reaction (b) (peak at 341 nm). Complex 6 of the mechanism may be a mixed valence complex⁵⁸ $[\text{Fe}_2^{\text{II}} \text{Fe}^{\text{III}} \text{O} (\text{NHOH})(\text{O}_2\text{CMe})_6]$ absorbing strongly⁵⁹ in the UV region. The scheme of the mechanism shows how the two products are obtained in two different conditions. The most significant observation consistent with the mechanism is that no gas is evolved in the presence of methyl methacrylate (mma), though Fe^{III} is reduced. Since a gas is evolved only after reaction (40) has occurred, it is obvious that the reactive intermediates formed in the forward reaction (39) are consumed by mma, and the reaction stops after 5 and 6. Thus the stoichiometry of the reaction in the presence of mma is 1 : 1 for both dark and light sensitive reactions.

Oxidation of hyponitrous acid

Another compound of nitrogen which can undergo

Mechanism of Fe^{III} and NH_3OH^+ reaction in acetate buffers.

multi-electron oxidation yielding different products, is hyponitrous acid ($H_2N_2O_2$) or hyponitrite. Unlike oxidation of hydroxylamine, the oxidation of hyponitrite does not seem to depend on the initial ratio of the reactants. To some extent the stoichiometry depends on pH. However, complications are produced with respect to stoichiometry and mechanism on account of subsequent reactions of one of the products with one of the reactants or amongst the products themselves as mentioned in the oxidation of hydroxylamine with Tl^{III} .⁵⁴

Sodium hyponitrite (70–90% purity) could be prepared by electrolytic reduction⁶⁰ of nitrite. It contained Na_2CO_3 as impurity but no nitrite. It has λ_{max} ⁶¹ at 247 nm, $\epsilon = 6550 M^{-1} s^{-1}$ in 0.1 M NaOH. It is reported to exist in two forms, *trans*- and *cis*-, and the latter is said to be unstable in decomposition^{62,63} and other reactions⁴⁰. The immediate oxidation product of $H_2N_2O_2$ is reported to be $H_2N_2O_3$, beta-oxyhyponitrous acid or trioxodinitrate(II) or peroxonitrite (NOO^- in alkaline solutions, an isomer of NO_2^-). There is no positive evidence for $H_2N_2O_3$ since the products are N_2O and HNO_2 obtained from the decomposition⁶³ in acid solutions (42).

This also is believed to be in two forms, alpha and beta and it is the beta form which is unstable and said to be formed in acid solutions. If oxyhyponitrous acid (λ_{max} 240 nm, $\epsilon = 8 \times 10^3$ in 0.1 M NaOH)⁶⁶ is prepared and treated with oxidants, it partly decomposes and partly gets oxidised, beta form corresponding to fast decomposition and alpha form to slow reaction. It is also possible that only reactive beta form is formed which on decomposition gives HNO_2 through reaction (42) and it is only the oxidation of HNO_2 which corresponds to the slow redox reaction and not the oxidation of the other form of oxyhyponitrous acid.

In most cases oxidant has been determined for stoichiometric experiments since no method for the determination of hyponitrous acid works in the presence of the constituents of the reaction mixture. Stoichiometric determinations with a number of oxidants and the probable scheme of reaction are shown below. The immediate oxidation product is supposed to be $H_2N_2O_3$. This after *D* has two options, (1) oxidation (*K*) and (2) decomposition (*E*). Similarly HNO_2 after (*E*) has three options, (1) oxidation (*L*), (2) decomposition (*F*) and (3) reaction with $H_2N_2O_2$ (*H*).

Stoichiometry of Tl^{III} oxidation could be determined

Figures in parentheses are the stoichiometries ($\Delta[\text{oxidant}]/\Delta[H_2N_2O_2]$).

Stoichiometry, scheme of reaction and products in the oxidation of $H_2N_2O_2$.

under both the conditions, when Tl^{III} or $H_2N_2O_2$ was in excess, former being determined iodometrically and the latter being determined by the precipitation method⁶⁶. The reaction is fast and occurs within the time of mixing as follows (43),

and subsequent reaction is typical of the oxidation of HNO_2 with Tl^{III} with all its usual characteristics⁵⁵. Thus in the beginning the stoichiometry is 1 : 1 but if it is determined later, say after 2 h, the overall stoichiometry is 2 : 1 according to (44) since HNO_2 is oxidised as in (45).

It is doubtful whether oxyhyponitrous acid is formed after the fast reaction since the reaction mixture does not show absorption at 248 nm. Since EDTA (0.015 M) and NO_2^- (1×10^{-4} M) had to be employed for removing the induction period and to obtain reproducible results to study the kinetics, the stoichiometry was not definite in their presence, if $[HClO_4] < 1.0$ M, but if $[HClO_4] > 1.5$ M, HNO_2 formed in (43) reacts with $H_2N_2O_2$ as in (46)

and the overall definite stoichiometry 1 : 2 as in (47).

Valuable information is obtained about the oxidation of $H_2N_2O_2$ from the reaction of $H_2N_2O_3$ with Tl^{III} . The reaction was initiated by the addition of a solution of oxyhyponitrite. Four facts are obvious from these results. (1) There was a fast reaction between $H_2N_2O_3$ and Tl^{III} but the latter consumed was always less than that corresponding to 1 : 1 stoichiometry, indicating thereby that part of $H_2N_2O_3$ decomposed. Hence oxidation and decomposition of $H_2N_2O_3$ are competitive processes. (2) After the fast reaction, the magnitude of decrease in Tl^{III} was less with the increase in $[Tl^{III}]$ – a characteristic of the oxidation of HNO_2 with Tl^{III} . (3) If the reaction was initiated by the addition of Tl^{III} , $H_2N_2O_3$ already present in the reaction mixture decomposed completely into HNO_2 , and there was no initial fast reaction with Tl^{III} . Total Tl^{III} consumed corresponded to 1 : 1 stoichiometry. (4) In the

presence of EDTA, the fast reaction becomes slow – much slower than the oxidation of $H_2N_2O_2$ under similar conditions.

In sulphuric acid solutions of Ce^{IV} ,⁶⁷ the stoichiometry is 1 : 1 according to (48),

which is a combination of (49), (42) and (46).

However, a reaction⁵⁶ (50) is known to be fast and in fact faster⁶⁷ than (46) and this contradicts the quantitative yield if N_2 and HNO_3 as per (46) or (48).

Such an anomalous situation has been circumvented by assuming that it is not HNO_2 but an isomer $NOOH$ which is formed by the decomposition of $H_2N_2O_3$. The cleavage of $N=N$ bond would result in the formation of $NOOH$ and HNO , the latter dimerizing to yield N_2O and H_2O . There is no evidence for a fast reaction or any reaction between $NOOH$ and $H_2N_2O_2$ but the former can be oxidised to $ONOOH$ (peroxonitrite) which yields HNO_3 by internal rearrangement⁶⁸. However, such peroxo compounds are very unstable in acid solutions, and peroxonitrite⁶⁸ absorbs at 302 nm in alkaline solutions. Following mechanism has been suggested for the reaction of $H_2N_2O_2$ with Ce^{IV} in acid sulphate solutions.

Stoichiometry in acid perchlorate solution is 4 : 1 because reaction (50) occurs in preference to (46), the aquo and hydroxo species⁶⁹ of Ce^{IV} being much more reactive than the strong sulphato complexes⁷⁰ of Ce^{IV} for reaction (50), (51) and (52). The reaction in $HClO_4$ solutions is so fast that a method for the determination of $H_2N_2O_2$ by Ce^{IV} has been suggested⁶⁷.

The oxidation of hyponitrous acid with iodine⁷¹ in acetate buffer occurs as in (55) in the pH range 4 to 6 and

Table 2. Stoichiometry and mole fraction of gases in the reaction of $\text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ and iodine in acetate buffers at 35°C ;
volume of reaction mixture = 100 cm^3

$10^3[\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]$		$10^3[\text{I}_2]$	$[\text{I}^-]$	pH	$\Delta[\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]/\Delta[\text{I}_2]$	mole of gas per mole of $\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$			Possible reactions (major/minor)	$\Delta[\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]/\Delta[\text{I}_2]$ calculated from		
mol dm^{-3}						N_2O	$\dot{\text{N}}\text{O}$	N_2		N_2O	NO	N_2
2.440	3.918	0.025	4.30	1.04 ^a								
2.440	5.877	0.025	4.30	1.03 ^a								
2.440	7.836	0.025	4.30	1.02 ^a								
2.440	9.795	0.025	4.30	1.05 ^a								
3.705	8.128	0.025	4.30	1.00 ^a								
3.705	6.096	0.025	4.30	1.07 ^a								
1.202	3.920	0.010	4.30	1.07								
1.202	5.880	0.015	4.30	1.04	0.493	0.665	0.035	(D) + (E) + (F)/(H)	1.01	1.00	-	
1.202	7.840	0.020	4.30	1.04								
1.316	5.060	0.025	4.30	1.03	0.490	0.687	0.034	(D) + (E) + (F)/(H)	1.02	0.97	-	
1.620	5.065	0.025	4.30	1.02	0.456	0.667	0.027	(D) + (E) + (F)/(H)	1.09	1.00	-	
1.934	5.061	0.025	4.30	1.00	0.470	0.646	0.046	(D) + (E) + (F)/(H)	1.06	1.03	-	
1.357	5.230	0.025	4.30	1.03	0.486	0.590	0.032	(D) + (E) + (F)/(H)	1.03	1.12	-	
1.575	5.010	0.025	5.74	1.02	0.501	0.665	0.28	(D) + (E) + (F)/(H)	0.99	1.00	-	
1.050	5.010	0.025	4.99	1.02	0.498	0.643	0.21	(D) + (E) + (F)/(H)	1.00	1.01	-	
1.880	4.680	0.000	4.30	0.98 ^{a,b}								
2.774	4.680	0.000	3.42	1.97 ^b	0.654	0.341	-	(D) + (E) + (F) + (H)/-	-	1.95	-	
1.900	4.160	0.010	5.57	1.01 ^c	0.500	0.00	0.90	(D) + (E) + (I)/-	1.00	-	1.02	
1.116	4.950	0.025	3.42	5.57 ^c	0.914	0.00	0.17	(D) + (E) + (I) + (J)/-	-	-	6.00	
1.183	5.010	0.200	4.27	2.96 ^c	0.821	0.02	0.33	(D) + (E) + (I) + (J)/(G)-	-	-	3.00	
1.700	4.350	0.011	3.42	4.7	0.880	0.14	0.01	(D) + (E) + (J) + (F)/(G)	4.8	-	-	
1.050	4.350	0.011	3.42	4.6	0.910	0.15	0.02	(D) + (E) + (J) + (F)/(G)	4.4	-	-	
1.500	4.350	0.185	4.05	3.3	0.806	0.22	0.00	(D) + (E) + (F) + (J)/(G)	-	3.00	-	
1.050	4.350	0.185	4.05	2.9	0.805	0.26	0.00	(D) + (E) + (F) + (J)/(G)	-	2.56	-	
1.202	4.064	0.100	4.90	1.52								
1.126	4.000	0.500	5.23	2.55 ^a								
1.126	6.000	0.100	5.23	1.28 ^a								
1.126	4.060	0.050	5.23	1.12 ^a								

Reactions : $\text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2 + \text{I}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3 + 2\text{H}^+ + 2\text{I}^-$ (D); $\text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}\text{N}_2\text{O} + \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{HNO}_2$ (E); $3\text{HNO}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{NO} + \text{HNO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (F); $2\text{HNO}_2 + 2\text{H}^+ + 2\text{I}^- \rightarrow 2\text{NO} + \text{I}_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (G); $\text{HNO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + \text{HNO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (H); $\text{HNO}_2 + \text{NH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H} \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (I); $\text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{N}_2\text{O} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (J)

^aNitrogen atmosphere. ^bAlcoholic iodine and no KI. ^cIn the presence of $0.0416\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ sulphamic acid.

at $[\text{I}^-] < 0.025\text{ M}$ with a stoichiometry ($\Delta[\text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]/\Delta[\text{I}_2]$) of 1 : 1 which otherwise becomes as different as 6 : 1 depending on the

conditions as given Table 2. One or more of the following reactions (G), (H) and (J) accompany the main reac-

tions (D), (E) and (F), if pH is < 4 and $[\text{I}^-] > 0.04\text{ M}$.

Table 3. Stoichiometry and gaseous products of reaction between $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ and $\text{N}_2\text{O}_2^{2-}$ in alkaline solutions $[\text{NaOH}] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; 35° ; volume of reaction mixture = 100 ml

$10^2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^2[\text{N}_2\text{O}_2^{2-}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]_{\text{final}}$ (mol dm^{-3})	Mole of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$ reacting with one mole of $\text{N}_2\text{O}_2^{2-}$	Volume of N_2 (ml) ^a	Volume of ($\text{N}_2 + \text{N}_2\text{O}$) (ml) ^a
1.00	0.50	0.395	1.21	10.3 (10.4)	15.9 (16.0)
2.00	1.00	0.810	1.19	10.1 (10.4)	15.8 (16.0)
2.10	1.00	0.890	1.21	10.4 (10.4)	16.0 (16.0)
2.30	1.50	0.485	1.21	15.7 (15.6)	23.7 (24.0)
3.10	1.50	1.26	1.23	14.8 (15.6)	23.2 (24.0)
4.00	2.00	1.60	1.20	21.0 (20.8)	31.6 (32.0)
6.00	3.00	2.34	1.22	11.8 (12.5)	18.0 (19.2)

^a Values in parentheses are the volumes on the basis of 1.21 : 1 stoichiometry.

The stoichiometry becomes larger than 1 : 1 on account of both the facts that more of $\text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ is consumed and less of iodine is used up or iodine is produced in the system. Normally $\text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ does not decompose⁷² in its redox reactions but in the presence of iodide it is greatly catalysed⁷¹, and so also by NO , HNO_2 and acidity⁷³. Thus iodide which had to be employed to bind iodine, has a great role in modifying the stoichiometry but the main reaction (D) which is rate controlling with HN_2O_2^- as the reactive species, does not change. The additional steps are (56) and (57),

and stoichiometry and mechanism are not changed. They certainly modify the rate law which becomes as (58)

$$-d[\text{I}_2]/dt = kK_d [\text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2][\text{I}_2]/[\text{H}^+](1 + K[\text{I}^-]) \quad (58)$$

k and K were found to be $2.1 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and 549 M^{-1} respectively at 35° under limiting conditions.

Yet another interesting case of stoichiometry and mechanism is the oxidation of hyponitrite by hexacyanoferrate(III)⁷⁵ in alkaline solutions where stoichiometry could be determined by estimating excess oxidant only. Stoichiometry ($\Delta[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]/\Delta[\text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]$) was neither 1 : 1 nor 4 : 1 as expected but it was 1.21 : 1 and it was fixed for the range of concentrations studied as shown in Table 3. Obviously the reaction occurs by two paths. The prod-

ucts were N_2 , N_2O and peroxonitrite. The mixtures were pale yellow and gave a peak⁶⁸ at 302 nm. Formation of N_2 and such low consumption of one electron oxidant in stoichiometric experiments could be explained only through the reduction of hyponitrite by some intermediate. No decomposition^{41b,53,72} of hyponitrite would occur in the pH range employed. Thus the reaction occurs as,

Initial reaction :

Path 1 :

Overall reaction :

Path 2 :

Overall reaction :

93% reaction occurs by path 1 of stoichiometry 1 : 1 and 7% reaction occurs by path 2 of stoichiometry 4 : 1, and this yields an overall stoichiometry of 1.21 : 1. Reaction mixtures containing excess $N_2O_2^{2-}$ if acidified, give back exactly original amount of $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$. This shows that there is some oxidant (not nitrate or nitrite) in the system which oxidises $Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$ in acid medium. This leaves peroxonitrite as the active oxidant species in the system. The absorption spectra of reaction mixtures containing excess of hyponitrite in 0.1 M NaOH exhibited peak at 302 nm which is characteristic of peroxonitrite ($\epsilon = 1670 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Thus the product appears to be peroxonitrite which finally gives nitrate.

Analysis of Tl^{III} - Sb^{III} system for stoichiometry of 1 : 1

It may be worthwhile to describe the stoichiometry of Tl^{III} - Sb^{III} reaction⁷⁶ in acid perchlorate solutions, not because the stoichiometry is complicated but because the determination of stoichiometry itself is complicated since there is precipitation and adsorption of the constituents during the reaction. However, a careful and patient analysis leads to the stoichiometry of 1 : 1.

Known volumes of the perchloric acid (1.5 M) solutions of Tl^{III} and Sb^{III} were allowed to react at 60° for about two hours. A precipitate was obtained, the colour of which varies from green (excess Tl^{III} to yellowish white (excess Sb^{III})). The precipitate was filtered off and washed 3-4 times with water. The filtrate and the washings were collected in a measuring flask and made up to 250 ml with water - [Solution (A)]. The precipitate was dissolved in 5.0 M HCl on heating and the resulting solution made up to 250 ml with water so as to yield a solution 2.5 M in HCl. This is [Solution (B)]. The concentrations of the various species in (A) and (B) were determined separately as follows.

Solution (A) : (a) Determination of Sb^{III} - a known excess of Ce^{IV} perchlorate solution was added to a known volume of the filtrate and diluted to yield $[H^+] = 0.15-0.20 \text{ M}$, and set aside for 8-10 min. The excess Ce^{IV} was back titrated against a standard solution of Fe^{II} ammonium sulphate to the ferroin end point; H_2SO_4 (0.5-1.0 M) was added to improve the end point. The Fe^{II} and Tl^{III} do not interfere with this method⁷⁷. Chloride ions ($>0.1 \text{ M}$) interfere.

(b) Sb^{III} and Tl^I together were determined bromometrically⁷⁸ in 2.5-3.5 M HCl using methyl orange as indicator.

(c) Total Sb^{III} - Tl^{III} and Sb^V were reduced by sulphite ions⁷⁹ and excess of the latter then removed as SO_2 by

boiling the solution. The total amount of Sb^{III} (that present initially plus that obtained by reduction of Sb^V) was determined using Ce^{IV} as in (a).

(d) The total amount of Tl^I and Sb^{III} in the reduced solution (c) was determined bromometrically⁷⁸.

Solution (B) : (e) The total amount of Sb^{III} and Tl^I in the solution (obtained from the precipitate) was determined bromometrically⁷⁸ without interference from Tl^{III} and Sb^V .

(f) Sb^V was reduced by sulphite ions and excess of the latter removed by boiling the solution. The total amount of Sb^{III} thus obtained was determined iodometrically⁸⁰ in a hydrogen carbonate ion medium.

(g) Tl^{III} was reduced in (f) and hence the total amount of Sb^{III} , Sb^V , Tl^I and Tl^{III} was determined bromometrically⁷⁸.

(h) Tl^{III} was precipitated as Tl^{III} -oxide by NaOH, centrifuged, washed and determined iodometrically^{15,81}. It was not possible to determine Sb^{III} in solution (B) using Ce^{IV} because the reaction between Ce^{IV} and Tl^I is catalysed⁷⁶ by chloride ions.

The concentrations of the different species in the filtrate and the precipitate were calculated as follows :

Filtrate (A)	Precipitate (B)
$[Sb^{III}] = a$	$[Tl^{III}] = h$
$[Sb^V] = (c - a)$	$[Tl^I] = g - f - h$
$[Tl^I] = (b - a)$	$[Sb^{III}] = e - (g - f - h)$
$[Tl^{III}] = (d - c) - (b - a)$	$[Sb^V] = g - e - h$

The results given in Table 4 show that one mole of Sb^{III} reacts with one mole of Tl^{III} to form one mole of Sb^V and one mole of Tl^I (with a maximum deviation of 10%). It is also obvious that the precipitate consists mainly of Sb^V with a small quantity of Tl^I . It also has adsorbed Tl^{III} or Sb^{III} whichever is in excess in the original mixture.

It was mentioned in the beginning that there is no correlation between variation in the stoichiometry and the mechanism of the reaction, nor was any indication given to make an attempt to do so. However, the variation in stoichiometry seems to be correlated to the type of redox system. In case of reactions between metal ions, if it is a complementary reaction⁸² with one-one electron change partners, stoichiometry will always be definite as in the oxidation⁸³ of iron(II) with Co^{III} and several other reactions. In case of two-two electron change reactants too, the stoichiometry will be definite⁷⁶ as in the case of Tl^{III} - Sb^{III} reaction⁷⁶ and the like reactions, provided the intermediate species of both the partners are

Table 4. Concentrations^a of the species Tl^I, Tl^{III}, Sb^{III} and Sb^V obtained in the filtrate (A) and precipitate (B) on reaction of the ions Tl^{III} and Sb^{III}

[Tl ^{III}] ₀ mmol l ⁻¹	[Sb ^{III}] ₀ mmol l ⁻¹	(A)				(B)			
		Tl ^{III}	Sb ^{III}	Tl ^I	Sb ^V	Tl ^{III}	Sb ^{III}	Tl ^I	Sb ^V
2.00	1.00	2.50		47.5	10.0	42.5		7.50	85.0
3.00	2.00	2.66		61.7	10.0	27.5		8.33	87.5
4.00	3.00	6.25		72.5	8.33	17.5		3.75	90.0
5.00	4.00	6.00		75.0	8.75	12.0		4.00	92.5
1.00	2.00		37.5	80.0	12.5		5.0	10.0	35.0
2.00	3.00		26.6	87.5	15.0		4.2	5.25	50.0
3.00	4.00		21.2	91.7	12.5		3.12	8.33	61.2
4.00	5.00		15.0	91.50	11.2		3.1	8.50	65.0
2.00	2.00			90.0	7.50			12.50	90.0
3.00	3.00			88.3	11.6			7.50	87.0
4.00	4.00			93.8	10.0			6.00	91.2
5.00	5.00			97.0	10.0			4.50	89.0

^aExpressed as a percentage of the concentrations of the reactants Tl^{III} and Sb^{III}.

reactive. If it is not so, the stoichiometry would not be fixed as found in the oxidation⁸⁴ of U⁴⁺ by Tl^{III} where the intermediate species UO₂⁺ could be stabilised.

In case of non-complementary reactions like those of V^{III} with Co^{III},⁸³ and Ce^{IV} with Cr^{III},⁸⁵ the stoichiometry is fixed because the intermediate species V^{IV}, Cr^{IV} and Cr^V are highly reactive. In the oxidation of Mn^{II},⁸⁶ with peroxodisulphate or the reduction of permanganate⁸⁷, the stoichiometry is likely to be complex unless the intermediate products are stabilised by complexing reagents or the reaction is carried out in a definite range of acidity/alkalinity or at fixed pH. The point to be highlighted is that wherever there is variation in the stoichiometry, the fact should be exploited to support a particular mechanism or suggest a probable different mechanism.

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